

SOCIO-ECONOMIC ISSUES OF PROFESSIONAL DIRECTION OF YOUTH ON THE BASIS OF GENDER APPROACH

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Abstract. In this article, the authors have studied the socio-economic issues of career orientation of young people based on the gender approach, and developed a scientific proposal and practical recommendations for the implementation of the world's best practices in our country.

Key words: education, science, knowledge and skills, scientific research and experimental design work, electronic navigator platforms, voucher, social lift, society, experience of foreign countries.

Introduction.

Today, important initiatives are being put forward in the academic circles of the country to increase the place and position of women, to educate young scientists of the new generation, and to encourage promising projects. Ensuring gender equality in various aspects of public life, including education and science, is one of the priorities of the internal political concept of Uzbekistan.

In this regard, the 69th goal of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026: provide women with education and professional skills, provide them with all-round assistance in finding a decent job, support their entrepreneurship, talented the task of identifying young women and directing their abilities is set[1].

Modern Uzbek society today is moving towards democratic development. One of the main principles of a democratic society is the recognition of equal rights of women and men in all spheres, which must be formed from a young age. This can be helped by the principles of gender approach in education. In the context of updating the content of education and modernization of general education schools, the problem of gender approach in education and upbringing of a person is becoming urgent.

Gender education helps to solve many important social problems, and the need for its development is increasingly being discussed in pedagogical communities. However, gender mainstreaming is still rare in school education in many countries. In the West, gender education and training begins in kindergarten.

The main part. Gender segregation exists in modern society, and it is divided into two forms of professional segregation, Horizontal and Vertical segregation, depending on gender.

Horizontal segregation occurs when men and women are divided by types of activity.

Vertical segregation is the distribution of men and women according to the hierarchy in a certain profession.

Gender segregation is carried out depending on the sum of psychological characteristics and characteristics of human social behavior. This often manifests itself in the form of existing

barriers to career advancement for women and men in society[2]. The term "glass ceiling" is also used to define gender segregation.

The theory of human capital, the theory of labor market segmentation, and gender theories are used to explain occupational segregation by gender.

According to human capital theory, women's lack of professional experience due to family responsibilities or interruptions in work due to childbirth causes them to be unable to acquire the skills that men possess. It follows that the productivity of women's work is naturally lower. However, with increasing competition, the number of educated and highly skilled workers of both sexes will increase. It is clear that under such conditions, women should be represented in most types of work, otherwise open discrimination against women will occur.

At the same time, Richard Anker's research shows that parents provide a higher level of education for their sons, so women are less likely to enter prestigious professions. The relationship between education and women's professional experience is two-way - despite equal rights in education and career choice, women's opportunities in the labor market are limited.

It should be noted that this theory is gradually losing its relevance, as the average age of marriage in the world has increased and the birth rate has decreased. In addition, most of the household chores are now performed automatically with the help of modern household appliances. These trends help to free up women's career development time and thereby increase their professional experience. However, no significant changes have been observed in the labor market so far, occupational segregation still exists.

In addition, employers use hidden discrimination mechanisms. According to women, family obligations prevent direct participation in continuous activities and work. This phenomenon is very common and manifests itself at the recruitment stage. The tendency of employers to discriminate against women formed the basis of G. Becker's theory. According to this theory, the costs of a discriminatory employer are higher than those of a non-discriminatory employer as a result of spending money and time to find only male workers.

According to the theory of labor market segmentation, market segmentation consists of dividing occupations into "male" and "female" [5]. Of course, scientific activity can be included in both categories. However, these theories are not aimed at explaining the causes of gender segmentation of occupations, but rather the predominance of men employed in a certain field. The reason for this division is the existence of stereotypes about "female" and "male" professions.

Usually, the introduction of a gender approach to the education system is hindered by factors such as ambiguous attitudes in society and the professional environment of teachers, the lack of special knowledge of school teachers in the field of gender pedagogy, and the fact that school curricula and textbooks are created without taking into account gender principles of education. can do.

At the same time, scientists say that "In modern society, there is a concept of male or female in certain professions"[6], and in fact, the labor market is currently characterized by a high level of gender asymmetry in the distribution of workers between professions. stands, which is manifested in the presence of "female" professions (hostesses, teachers, etc.) and "male" professions (military personnel, programmers, etc.).

V.V. Kozlov noted that gender asymmetry in the distribution of occupations leads to an increase in unemployment, difficulties in the process of employment, causes women to encounter psychological obstacles during the acquisition of "male" occupations, and vice versa.

Thus, at present, the gender approach to professional self-determination takes into account not only biological or physical differences between men and women, but also cultural and social aspects. In the research of scientists in the field of gender differences in the professional interests of adolescents, it was noted that the gender characteristics of adolescents affect their career choices.

Sergeeva's research on the gender characteristics of the motivational readiness of teenagers to choose specialized education revealed that there are specific characteristics in the preference of girls and boys. In particular, boys are more interested in "human-technical" professions, and girls are more interested in "human-art" professions.

The analysis of existing studies in the field of gender differences in professional interests of adolescents shows that, despite a sufficient amount of research in the field of professional education of students, the gender aspect of professional interests in young adolescents is an understudied field of scientific research.

Adolescence is one of the main stages of personal development and is accompanied by an identity crisis, within which life, professional and social self-determination takes place. In such conditions, girls and boys develop life views about their position among other people, self-awareness, psychosocial self-determination and readiness to choose a profession. It is during this age period that socio-psychological characteristics, built at three levels, taking into account gender characteristics, are noted:

- 1) internal (perception of oneself as a representative of a certain gender, attitude towards oneself);
- 2) interpersonal relations (perception by peers, attitude towards persons of the opposite sex, etc.);
- 3) interaction with the social environment (relation to relations with persons of the opposite sex, etc.).

The analysis of the results of the study of professional interests among young teenagers showed that the field of professional activity such as "physics-mathematics" is in the first place in terms of the number of choices among boys. and among girls, this field of professional activity received the greatest choice as "chemistry and biology". In our opinion, the existing differences in the fields of professional activity in young adolescents depend on the age and individual characteristics of students, their individual inclinations, ideas about the variety of professions, specific characteristics of teaching and learning. lib, which, in turn, shows the need to carry out targeted work on the formation of professional interests in young adolescents and create favorable conditions for their professional self-determination, taking into account gender differences.

Formation of professional self-determination in the process of studying at school becomes one of the targeted processes of evaluating oneself and one's capabilities in the future professional field. Researchers N. E. Kasatkina, E. A. Pakhomova and E. L. Rudnev understand professional self-determination as a complex decision-making process. Professional self-determination is an analysis of one's own internal resources, including abilities, in relation to professional requirements.

the process of independent choice of a profession. Factors of effective formation of professional self-determination are specialized forms of education, methods of extracurricular activities, social partnership with vocational guidance subjects, and the educational space in general.

In the field of career and professional orientation in foreign practice, the international creative association "life design" is active, consisting of professional guides from many countries of the European Union. European experts recommend taking into account the "theory of self-construction" and "theory of career construction" in the formation of professional self-determination of young people. A. Watts says that professional support serves both the individual and society as a whole. The process of professional self-determination is the result of many interrelated external and internal factors, including the gender approach.

Parents and relatives (36%), mass media (34), Internet resources (32), friends and acquaintances (27 %), teachers (22%) and lastly mention books (20%). There are also professional tests (15%), training with employment service specialists (5%).

Mass media and Internet resources, as well as many institutions of society, influence the choice of professions of schoolchildren and reinforce gender stereotypes. For example, in the media, women are mainly portrayed as the object of action, victims, and caring for others, while men are portrayed as inventive, strong, intelligent, and proactive. While the media emphasizes men's strength and success, women are often judged on their appearance. Thus, the mass media, including television, radio, textbooks, children's books, magazines, movies, and many forms of electronic communication, perpetuate and propagate stereotypes about men and women.

Also, students E.A. They answered the questions of the "differential diagnostic questionnaire" (DDO) methodology designed to select different types of professions according to Klimov's classification of professions. The obtained data show the differences between girls and boys in the choice of future professions. Thus, young people mainly choose professions in the fields of "human - technology" (49 percent), "human - signal system" (21 percent) and "human - human" (14 percent). Girls prefer the fields of "person - symbol system" (28 percent), "person - artistic image" (24 percent) and "person - person" (23 percent).

According to career guidance experts, this is due to high school students' classification of professions as "masculine" and "feminine", which significantly affects their professional self-determination. makes a secret. Compared to girls, boys are more clearly oriented towards technical professions. This is consistent with much of the data, which shows that from childhood to old age, men prefer technology-related careers.

According to the results of the "DDO" questionnaire and methodology, conclusions are made about priority occupations among high school students on gender issues. It turned out that the boys' favorite subjects are history (43%), computer science (31.2%), chemistry (31%), physics (27%), mathematics (26%), physical education (24%).) and English (21%).

Among girls, favorite school subjects are literature (41%), history (33%), social studies (30%) and English (27%). Thus, boys are more interested in the cycle of exact sciences and natural sciences, while girls prefer humanities.

Summarizing the above, it can be concluded that the most important factors affecting the choice of a profession of students of both sexes are personal characteristics: along with

abilities and interests, the advice of parents and relatives, friends and acquaintances is also important.

In conclusion, it was concluded that the vocational training of boys and girls is not a local, but a change of a conceptual nature, because it requires a change in the value system of society, a transition from a sex role to a gender approach in the process of vocational guidance of young people .

If the school continues to prepare boys and girls for various social roles and professions, the situation will not change. Officially, the education system does not prevent boys and girls from choosing a profession. However, from children's games, through textbooks, home economics classes for girls, and plumbers or carpentry for boys, stereotypes about the division of occupations into "male" and "female" are instilled into the minds of young people, and these stereotypes confirms that it continues to play an important role in selection. Therefore, all curricula and textbooks should be presented in a way that does not reinforce gender stereotypes of women.

For example, the percentage of women in the texts and images of high school English textbooks was 44% in Malaysia and Indonesia, 37% in Bangladesh, and 24% in the Punjab province of Pakistan. Gender stereotypes also persist in the Ethiopian education sector, which can be explained by the exclusion of women from the process of revising and developing textbooks.

Conclusions and suggestions:

- every school and college should have an established professional education and guidance program that is known and understood by students, parents, teachers, employers;
- every student and their parents are informed so that they have quality information about future educational and labor market opportunities, to reduce the risk of making decisions based on gender stereotypes, to make the most of the available information will need the help of a consultant;
- students have different career needs at different stages, so access to advice and support needs to be tailored to each student's needs, the school's careers programs are inclusive and diverse should include issues;
- every student should have multiple opportunities to learn from employers about jobs, employment and skills valued in the workplace. This can be done through a range of enrichment activities including visiting speakers, mentoring and corporate schemes;
- each student should have first professional experience in the workplace through a business trip, work observation or work experience to explore career opportunities and expand their networks;
- all students should fully understand the educational opportunities available to them, including academic and vocational courses, as well as training in schools, colleges, universities and workplaces;
- every student should have the opportunity to talk with a career counselor, which can be internal (school staff) or external. They should be trained at the appropriate level, which should be organized differently depending on their individual needs.

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